

Microstructure and Mechanical Strength of Vacuum Brazing Bonded Ti_3SiC_2 Joints Using Al interlayer

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SUMMARY

Ti_3SiC_2 is one of the nanolayered ternary ceramics $M_{n+1}AX_n$, where M is a transition metal, A is an A-group (mostly IIIA or IVA) element, and X is C or N. It possesses a unique combination of the merits of both metals and ceramics^[1-2]. And it attracts considerable attention because of its remarkable properties such as low density, high strength, and elastic modulus, a high ratio of fracture toughness to strength, damage tolerance at room temperature, metallic electrical conductivity, good machinability, excellent thermal shock resistance and oxidation resistance^[3]. These unusual combinations of the properties render it a candidate structural material for high-temperature applications^[4-5]. Although synthesis technology and property characterization of Ti_3SiC_2 bulk material have been widely investigated, its practical engineering application is still limited. Similar to other ceramics, the synthesis of bulk Ti_3SiC_2 with big dimensions and complex shapes is also difficult in practice. This limitation can be overcome by joining suitable components together to get the required dimensions. Therefore, studies on the joining of Ti_3SiC_2 with metals or ceramics are significant for promoting its applications. Vacuum brazing of Ti_3SiC_2 joints by using Al interlayer has been conducted at temperatures of 800°C–950°C for 5-10min under 3.5×10^3 Pa in a vacuum furnace. The phase composition and microstructure of the joints were investigated by x-ray diffraction, scanning electron microscopy, and electron probe microanalysis. Based on investigations of phase composition, microstructure, and shear strength of joints, the reaction process of the reaction layer at the Ti_3SiC_2 /Al interface have been discussed. The growth of the reaction layer follows parabolic law and the diffusion of aluminum through the reaction zone toward Ti_3SiC_2 is the main controlling step in the bonding process. Joint strengths were determined through shear tests. The maximum high temperature shears strength of 112 ± 10 MPa, which is only 75% of the shear strength of Ti_3SiC_2 at the same testing condition.

Keywords: Ti_3SiC_2 /Al/ Ti_3SiC_2 Joints, vacuum brazing, microstructure, growth kinetics , mechanical strength

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The bulk Ti_3SiC_2 used in this work was synthesized by self-propagation high temperature combustion synthesis with pseudo hot isostatic pressing (SHS/PHIP) technology. Ti_3SiC_2 was cut into rectangular solid samples with dimensions of 3 mm×4

mm×3 mm. Al foil with 100μm depth was cut to the same area. These entire sample surfaces were ground to 500-1500 grit SiC paper and polished with W3.5 and W0.5 diamond paste, sequentially, and ultrasonically cleaned in acetone before joining. Vacuum brazing was carried out in a vacuum resistance furnace (ZDL-3; Hangxin Inc., Jinzhou). Two rectangular specimens with Al filler inside that contacted face to face were located in a graphite jig in the vacuum chamber, as illustrated in Fig. 1.

The bonding temperature and time were selected in the range of 800°C–950°C and 5-10 min, respectively. The vacuum inside the chamber was kept below 5×10^{-3} Pa. A uniaxial pressure of 3.5×10^3 Pa was applied perpendicularly to the bonding interface. Parameters such as temperature, pressure and time, were automatically controlled during the brazing process. First the sample was heated to 300°C at the rate of 10°C/min and then sustained about 30min in order to make cyanoacrylate adhesive fully volatilize. Secondly, the sample continued to be heated to 800°C–950°C at 10°C/min and keep the temperature about 5-10min. At the end of brazing, the sample was cooled to 200°C at 5°C/min under the same bonding pressure, and the pressure was then released and the sample was cooled to room temperature. The thermal cycle of the brazing is shown in Fig. 2.

Ti₃SiC₂/Al Joints were prepared and polished for shear strength measurements. Shear tests were performed on INSTRON5569 testing machine using a specially designed holder, as illustrated in Fig. 3. The position of the specimen could be adjusted and fixed so that the shear force was applied to the joint. The jig was machined deliberately and all fittings could be kept fine matched and the contact width of the jig was approximately 1 mm so that the normal stresses generated in specimens could keep a minimal value. Martinelli et al.²⁸ and X.H.Yin et al used a similar method to determine the shear strength of Si₃N₄/Mo joints and Ti₃SiC₂/Ni joints respectively. During the tests, the crosshead speed was 0.5 mm/min.

The joint interfaces were investigated by a scanning electron microscope (SEM; HITACHI S-4700) equipped with energy-dispersive spectroscopy. The distributions of elements were determined by electron probe microanalysis (EPMA; EPMA1610; Shimadzu, Tokyo, Japan). The phase compositions of the reaction zone were identified by X-ray diffraction (XRD) using Cu K α radiation (D/max-RB; Rigaku Instruments, Tokyo, Japan).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Electron Probe Microanalysis (EPMA) of the braze joint

Fig.4 exhibits the concentration penetration profile of the Ti₃SiC₂ and Al joints interface. Quantitative electron probe microanalyses (EPMA) of the Ti₃SiC₂ and Al brazed at 950 °C suggests that the joining process is due to the interdiffusion of Ti, Si towards the filler alloy and Al towards ceramic matrix, which leads to the formation of the Ti₃SiC₂/Al interface. From Fig. 1 it is observed that the diffusion depth of Al is about 16 μm and the diffusion depth of Ti is about 4μm. In addition, the growth of the reaction layer follows parabolic law. This indicated that at the interface Al first reacts with the Ti from Ti₃SiC₂ to reform some intermetallic phase TiAl₃. It has been reported

elsewhere [6-7] that the diffusivity of Al controls the kinetics of the formation of the reaction products at the interface. Besides, the C content is not very accurate by EPMA.

Phase composition

Ti₃SiC₂ and Al joints interface was formed at the condition that the brazing temperature is 950°C and the holding time is 10min and the XRD analysis was carried. Fig.5 presents X-ray diffraction patterns of the Ti₃SiC₂ and Al joints interface. From Fig.2 it is observed that the phase composition mainly includes TiC, TiAl₃ and the remaining Al. During the brazing process, the Ti element from Ti₃SiC₂ would react with liquid Al. Furthermore small amount of Si element would diffuse into the liquid Al to form Al(Si) solid solution. At the meanwhile, the C element from the Ti₃SiC₂ would react with the Ti to form TiC. The whole reaction equation is as followed:

Microstructure of joints

Fig. 6 presents backscattered electron images of Ti₃SiC₂/Al joints brazed at different temperature for the same holding time using Al filler. From the above figure, with the increasement of brazing temperature, the reaction degree between the filler and ceramic also increase. It is well known that a higher temperature is beneficial to improve the reaction activity. The origin depth of Al filler is 100μm, and after a certain time, the width of interface region is about 50μm, it is verified that the liquid Al has dissolved into the ceramic. Combined with the results of XRD and EMPA, liquid Al is certain to react with Ti element to form the TiAl₃ (gray part in the Fig.6). Obviously, the amount of TiAl₃ takes on an tendency of increase. In addition, the remaining Ti and C in the Ti₃SiC₂ matrix will react with each other to form TiC (black part in the Fig.6) at the interface region.

Joint shear strength

Joint strengths were determined through shear tests. The maximum high temperature shears strength of 112±10MPa is only 75% of the shear strength of Ti₃SiC₂, whose shear strength is about 150±13MPa at the same testing condition.

CONCLUSION

Ti₃SiC₂ ceramic can be joined using Al filler under 850~950°C with holding time of 5~10 minutes by vacuum brazing technology. The phase composition of interface region is about 50μm, which mainly includes Al, TiAl₃ and TiC. EMPA results showed that the diffusion rate of Al controlled the whole reaction process. Besides, the shear strength of joints showed that the joint shear strength is lower than the Ti₃SiC₂ matrix materials.

Fig. 1 Schematic illustration of the assembly for joints brazing

Fig. 2 Thermal cycle for vacuum brazing of Ti_3SiC_2/Al joints

Fig. 3 Schematic illustration of the assembly for shear strength testing of joints

Fig. 4 EPMA line profile analyses of the Ti_3SiC_2/Al brazed interface

Fig. 5 X-ray diffraction patterns of the Ti_3SiC_2 and Al joints interface

Fig.6 Backscattered electron images of Ti_3SiC_2/Al joint brazed at (a) 800°C; (b) 850°C;

(c) 950°C using Al filler

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Program for Changjiang Scholars and Innovative Research Team in University (PCSIRT0615).

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